

Effect of Info-Savvy skills on achievement of Curriculum Development on Moodle platform

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Abstract

Up gradation of technology leads to a digital world of education, where everything is available at one click. This makes the education system more flexible as well as interesting. To keep this in mind researcher work on Moodle platform, which is a free online teaching learning platform. This research paper aims to identify the effect of Info-Savvy skills of students on the achievement of curriculum development content on Moodle platform. The sample consists of B.Ed. students of school of education Davv Indore, M.P. A standardized rating scale was used to identify the Info-Savvy Skills in the sample group and after the completion of Moodle course; both the data were compared to identify the effect. Researcher found that the students who uses their Info-Savvy skills always in there work will score higher in the course while those who uses rarely their info savvy skills were score below average.

1.1.0 Introduction

Technology is becoming a part of daily life of every individual. As most of the work done in home and office require one or the other Technology. Similarly Technology eradicated the gaps between the generations. Even in different fields the Technology plays an important role, in the form of ICT, instruments, online platforms, etc. Now days there are several online platforms which are used in education. These platforms offer various features to make learning

interesting and flexible, which leads to a better understanding of the concepts. Some of these platforms are Moodle, Coursera, EduX, Eureka etc.

All these platform runs with the help of internet on a local media such as laptop, mobile or desktop. Also most of the platform offers free access to their features. But internet surfing plays an important role in students learning. As whether students were able to access the information? How much? Searching in desired order? Etc. On the one hand all the information is available on the web but on the other side if a person not able to select or search out the information correctly it is of no use. So to identify the skill of searching information from web, Info-Savvy Skills can be assessed.

In this present paper following research questions will be dealt:

1. Whether the Info-Savvy Skills affect the achievement of students in online mode?
2. Whether high Info-Savvy Skilled students always achieve high scores?

1.1.1 Moodle

Moodle is an open online learning platform where anyone can create a course and can teach a huge number of pupils. It can be customaries as per the need of the course. The Moodle abbreviation denotes the Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment. As the name itself explain the features of Moodle platform that is, it is a Modular structure with specific sequencing of content, Object-Oriented as it is a programming language that consist of several objects which can be controlled and modified during the course. It is Dynamic in nature because the program is upgrading time to time hence the course interface and features also changes accordingly. And it Programmed for the learning purpose which create a learning environment for the individual as per their pace.

1.1.2 Info-Savvy Skills

Info savvy skills are the ways through which a person thinks systematically, search and analysis logically, able to collect data scientifically and apply it in daily life. It is also considered the use of internet and keeping information up to date. If a person possesses these skills then these skills are known as Info-Savvy.

There are five dimensions of Info-Savvy skills that is Asking Skill, Accessing Skill, Analyzing Skill, Applying Skill and Assessing Skill.

1.2.0 Review of related literature

On reviewing the research studies related with the variables fewer number of researches were found on the effectiveness of MOODLE that were done by Salhab (2019) on attitudes of faculty members at PTUK university towards MOODLE; Yafaei and Attamimi (2019) on implementation of MOODLE by Omani English language teachers; Sonmez and Mustafa (2018) on experiences of pre-service teachers taking a course through MOODLE; Khoza (2016) on managers reflections on their use of visions of MOODLE for curriculum management; Stasinakis and Kalogiannakis (2015) on MOODLE at secondary level in Greece; Oproiu (2014) on MOODLE in University teaching process; Chourishi, Buttan, Chaurasia, and Soni (2012) on exploring the implementation of effective E-learning through MOODLE at various colleges; Wood (2010) on Technology for Teaching and Learning: MOODLE as a Tool for Higher Education; Wood (2010) on Hybrid Technologies for Teaching and Learning in Higher Education: Access and Prior Experience on B.Ed. students.

Also, Very few studies conducted on different Pedagogy were found by the researcher are Pandey(2020) on the Effectiveness of developed MOODLE based on Psychological perspectives of B.Ed. learners (India); Ferdiánová (2017) on the introduction of interactive materials for Monge projection in mathematics, which are implemented into LMS MOODLE; Gunduz and Ozcan

(2017) on students perception on using the MOODLE system in a secondary school in English as a foreign language lesson.; Seifert (2017) on using MOODLE in teaching for pre-service teacher education; Allen (2015) on Social media as an alternative to MOODLE in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teaching practice forums for teacher trainees; Hay and Dale (2014) on Moving through MOODLE: Using e-technology to enhance social work field education. There were only two studies related with Info-savvy skills by Purohit (2016) on implementing educational activities for exploring coping skills for the 21st century among students of secondary level and Dhodhi (2011) on teachers Development and implementation of a program for enhancing info savvy skills in student. But none of the research study was done on to identify the effect of Info-Savvy skills on curriculum development achievement at Moodle platform.

1.3.0 Methodology

1.3.1 Sample

The sample consists of 57 B.Ed. students of 20-22 session of School of education Davv Indore. In which 43 were female students and 14 were male students.

1.3.2 Tool

Info-Savvy rating scale was used to assess the Info-Savvy Skills of students. Info-Savvy skills Rating scale was constructed and standardized by the researcher prior to the administration on the sample group. This rating scale is consist of 21 statements (7 negative and 14 positive statements) which was rated on 5 points as Always, often, sometimes, rarely and never which were score as 5,4,3,2,1 for positive and 1,2,3,4,5 for negative statements respectively. An average was calculated for all the statements of rating scale points (Always, often, sometimes, rarely and never).

1.3.3 Procedure

The B.Ed. group was taught through Moodle based on curriculum development. There were 3 units taken from the B.Ed. course of SOE, DAVV, and Indore. The total time period of teaching was 8 weeks.

The steps of administration of moodle were as follows:

1. Orientation of Moodle and its uses were given to students
2. Every student was allotted a user ID and password for handling the Moodle.
3. Weekly sections were designed by the administrator of the curriculum course.
4. After every unit there was a quiz for checking students understanding.

Fig 1. Home page of the Moodle site developed by the researcher

Through this procedure student completed the curriculum development course on Moodle platform and they score the total of all the quizzes. And these scores were taken for the analysis.

1.4.0 Analysis of the data

Analysis of the data obtained from Info-Savvy Skill rating scale was converted into percentage for five points, depicted in table 1. Analysis of data obtained from Moodle course were also divided into 5 levels that is high, above average, average and below average and low.

Table 1:

Percentage of average calculated for each rating point

Rating points	Percentage
Always	32.50
Often	33.08
Sometimes	24.14
Rarely	7.27
Never	3.01

The total marks obtained in Moodle were converted into percentage and then divide it into 5 equal levels that is High, Above average, Average, Below average, and low. The data obtained were represented in table 2.

Table 2:

Percentages of score obtained at each level

Level of scores	Percentage
High	36.84
Above Avg	7.02
Avg	45.61
Belowavg	10.53
Low	0

1.5.0 Interpretation and discussion

By observing the above values (table 1 and table 2 both), it is clear that those who always use the Info-Savvy Skills during the Moodle course were score higher that is 33 % use Info-Savvy skills and 37 percent students got the high marks that is between 80-100 %. Similarly 7 % students rarely use Info-Savvy Skills in their work so they achieve below average marks that is between 20-40%.

But the students those uses Info-Savvy Skills often and sometimes were separately not resemble with the scores obtained at above average and average but by considering both the cases together that is often and sometimes is $33+24=57\%$ students, scores average and above average marks that is 52% students got marks between 40 to 80 % were elicited that students those uses info savvy skill often or sometime can achieve average or above average marks at online platform. There were no students who score lowest marks that is 0-20 % but there were some students who uses Info-Savvy Skills that is 3% and they belong to below average category.

For first research question: Whether the Info-Savvy Skills affects the achievement of students in online mode?

Yes it can be observed from the data analysis that the info savvy skill scores are related with the marks obtained in Moodle platform. 32% of the students uses info savvy skills while 37% students score higher marks, it means students achieve higher marks if they uses info savvy skills. Similarly the scores decrease with decreasing level of info savvy skills, it means if student not use info savvy skill it affects its performance in online performance. For second research question: Whether high Info-Savvy Skilled students always achieve high scores?

By observing the results it can be said that a higher info savvy skilled student get higher marks as he/she can surf the internet and explore the content

easily and effectively. This will help him/her in better online performance. But of course it can also be elicited that those who uses info savvy often or sometime can also be achieve higher score as the scores of higher percentage in table 2 is 36% and those of always in table 1 is 32%. Similarly, by observing the data of low marks category includes 0% students but never category of table 1 shows 3% of students which reveals that, if a student never use or not able to use info savvy skills in their work can achieve certain marks.

1.6.0 Conclusion

This research paper focuses basically on the effect of Info-Savvy skills of student those studying in online mode. As during online teaching they have to surf the internet for searching different topics, concepts, examples, information etc. But due to individual differences every student not able to perform the same task equally. So, it is quite clear from the above analysis that if a student surf the internet properly and regularly as per the instruction their performance increases while if not, the performance decrease. Hence, it can be said that the achievement in Curriculum Development is dependent on Info-Savvy Skills of students. On the other hand it can also be elicited that as the percentage of info savvy not exactly similar with that of score level, in some cases the info-savvy skill less affect the performance in online mode.

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